

Brussels, 26 May 2021

Certificate of Award

Julián Atilio Puszkiel

was awarded in 2019 a

MARIE SKŁODOWSKA-CURIE Fellowship

as part of the EU-funded project

ACCIÓ programme to foster mobility of researchers with
a focus in applied research and technology transfer
(TECNIOspring PLUS)

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read "B Arano", with a long, sweeping horizontal stroke extending to the right.

Begoña Arano
Head of Department 'Excellent Science'
Research Executive Agency